

**HUMAN-MACHINE RELATIONSHIP IN EDUCATION: POSSIBLE SCENARIO IN 5
YEARS' TIME**

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***Abstract.** Due to changes in the education sector and technological advancements, careers of university lecturers are anticipated to undergo substantial changes in the future. The advantage in employment will be given to teachers who can quickly adapt to new trends. New requirements for a new generation teacher - to have digital competencies, be flexible, able to adapt a lesson to any conditions and formats, be able to keep the attention of the audience in any situation, such as learning on digital platforms - teacher-coordinator, blended learning - teacher-mentor, focus on practical skills - teacher-practitioner.*

***Keywords:** artificial intelligence, education, human-machine relationship, online learning, virtual reality, and augmented reality*

In a lecture titled "The Terror of Change", Patricia Gulas Strauch cited three aspects of our future about which there is little disagreement: the speed of change will accelerate; the world will be increasingly complex; and nations and world issues will be increasingly interdependent. In the history of mankind, technological revolutions have always accumulated for a long time and gradually, but sooner or later a trigger led to a quick restructuring of both economies and public relations. The latest technologies that have developed exponentially over the past two decades have only been waiting for a trigger a new grand transformation of society. Covid-19 has served as such trigger. The market of distance education, the benefits of which the experts argued lazily, is beginning to dominate the traditional university. In a matter of weeks, new online services appeared which only the most daring futurologists had previously spoken about (Elinson, 2020).

AI lecturers might become a standard fixture at universities in the future because to technological advancements. The prospect of replacing lecturers with artificial intelligence (AI) computers is now being considered, but it is rarely discussed. This could sound futuristic because teaching is still regarded as being too creative for computers on lists of professions susceptible to AI. However, a rising body of data gleaned from online courses, including clickstreams, eye-tracking, and even emotion detection, may one day make AI professors a familiar sight (Haw, 2019). University lecturer`s 18% of job is susceptible for automation (ABC, 2023). Some of university lecturer tasks that are easier to automate are:

- monitor student performance
- write grant proposals
- maintain student records
- create technology-based learning materials
- develop instructional materials
- write articles, books or other original materials in area of expertise.

82% of work time on tasks that are less susceptible to automation (ABC, 2023). Some of university lecturer tasks that are difficult to automate are:

- evaluate effectiveness of educational programs
- assess educational needs of students
- administer tests to assess educational needs or progress
- evaluate student work
- compile specialized bibliographies or lists of materials
- select educational materials or equipment

The day when AI completely replaces lecturers is probably still a few years away (Haw, 2019). Due to changes in the education sector and technological advancements, careers of lecturers are anticipated to undergo substantial changes in 5 year future. Future career trends for lecturers could include any of the following:

-increasing use of technology: Platforms, such as coursera.org and canvas network, will be game changers. Professors may employ online learning, virtual reality, and augmented reality to connect with students and offer lectures.

-focus on interdisciplinary research: Professors may collaborate across disciplines more often to address challenging global issues.

-the importance of lifelong learning is stressed since academics may need to refresh their knowledge and abilities throughout their careers due to the quick rate of technological change. Self-development should be lifelong task. Since we are living in uncharted and challenging waters, and knowledge we have gained today may not be enough or even competent at all tomorrow, self-development should be continues process of individual change.

- Daily basis processes I carry out in teaching and accounting are repetitive. I expect in near future, both of my jobs will be carried out by AI. As a part of strategy for future challenges, now I am learning to create educational app. Thus I am also majoring in mobile app inventing.

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